

Platinum Group Elements, Shocked Quartz, and Nanodiamonds in Greenland Ice Consistent with an Extraterrestrial Impact at the Younger Dryas Onset 12,800 Years Ago: Supporting Information

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Supporting Information, Figures

Figure S1. Mass Distribution of Fe-Rich Nanoparticles in Greenland Ice Across the Bølling-Allerød, Younger Dryas, and Holocene Intervals. A heat map showing binned mass distributions of Fe-rich nanoparticles detected in Greenland ice samples using single-particle inductively coupled plasma time-of-flight mass spectrometry (SP-ICP-TOF-MS). Rows represent sampled depths from 3.82 to 6.68 meters, spanning the Holocene, Younger Dryas (YD), and Bølling-Allerød (B/A) intervals. Columns denote increasing nanoparticle mass bins. Only iron-dominant nanoparticles (≥ 100 wt% Fe), including native Fe, wüstite, or iron oxides, are shown.

Color intensity reflects the abundance of particles per mass bin, with warmer shades indicating higher particle counts. The nanoparticles were extracted from the same mass of sediments in the same volume of water. A yellow line connects the mean mass-weighted position of peak particle abundance at each depth level. Vertical orange arrows indicate general trends in Fe-rich nanoparticle abundance and mass, highlighting a notable increase during the YD and continuing into the early Holocene.

An anomalous feature occurs at the YD onset, where a sharp decrease in Fe nanoparticle mass is observed, despite elevated counts above and below this point. This abrupt dip is interpreted as a transient depletion caused by atmospheric filtering or settling effects immediately following the Younger Dryas impact event, which may have vaporized or redistributed particulate matter. The subsequent increase in nanoparticle abundance and mass likely reflects post-impact injection of Fe-rich aerosols or sedimentary reworking under destabilized climate conditions. The sustained elevation of Fe nanoparticle mass into the Holocene may indicate longer-term atmospheric or depositional changes triggered by the impact event or ongoing climate perturbation.

Figure S2. Decline in Si-Rich Nanoparticle Mass near the Younger Dryas in Greenland Ice.

This figure displays a heat map of binned total mass for silicon-rich (Si-rich) nanoparticles detected in Greenland ice core samples, analyzed using single-particle inductively coupled plasma time-of-flight mass spectrometry (SP-ICP-TOF-MS). The stratigraphic interval spans from 6.68 to 3.82 meters in depth, encompassing the Bølling-Allerød (B/A), Younger Dryas (YD), and Holocene periods. The only nanoparticles included are those that contain Si—likely derived from continental silicate dust sources, such as quartz and feldspar. Columns represent increasing mass bins, with color intensity reflecting the range of total mass within each bin—warmer colors indicate increasing total mass. The yellow line represents the mean mass-weighted peak at each depth, and orange arrows indicate the overall stratigraphic trend within each climate interval. The nanoparticles were extracted from the same mass of sediments in the same volume of water.

Results show a pronounced and sustained decline in Si-nanoparticle mass close to the onset of the Younger Dryas (~5.47 m), extending throughout the YD and into the Holocene. This trend contrasts with that of Fe nanoparticles, which exhibit a post-impact increase in mass. The decline in silicate nanoparticle mass may reflect a reduction in long-range atmospheric dust transport following the Younger Dryas impact event, potentially driven by altered wind patterns or a shift in dust source regions. Alternatively, the trend may indicate preferential deposition or preservation of metal (e.g., Fe-dominant) aerosols over silicate-rich particles under impact-modified atmospheric conditions.

This observed pattern is counter to expectations, as the cooler and drier conditions during the Younger Dryas would likely have reduced snow accumulation, thereby concentrating atmospheric particulates, including silicates, in the ice. Instead, the decline in Si nanoparticle mass suggests that other mechanisms—such as impact-related atmospheric disruption, aerosol filtration, or changes in dust provenance—dominated the depositional regime during this interval. Collectively, the data support the interpretation that a significant atmospheric disturbance marked the onset of the Younger Dryas, consistent with a high-energy impact or airburst event that fundamentally altered global dust flux and aerosol composition.

Figure S3. Elevated Elemental Ratios of PGEs and Zn During the Younger Dryas Interval in Greenland Ice Samples. Profiles of bulk elemental mass ratios measured by inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) from a sediment core spanning the Holocene, Younger Dryas (YD), and Bølling-Allerød (B/A) intervals in Greenland. Panels (A–D) show ratios of PGE and Zn elements normalized to Ca (Pt/Ca, Ir/Ca, Ru/Ca, Zn/Ca), while panels (E–H) show inter-element ratios among platinum group elements (Pt/Pd, Ir/Pt, Pt/Ru, Pt/Rh). All ratios are expressed in ppb/ppb (parts per billion). The shaded blue band denotes the YD interval. Each plot shows a distinct and sustained enrichment in these ratios during the YD, with broad peaks centered at a core depth of approximately 5.0 m (middle YD). These enhancements likely reflect a climate-modulated geochemical signal rather than a discrete impact layer, suggesting sustained input of extraterrestrial-rich or volcanogenic aerosols, altered sedimentation rates, or redistribution of elements under changing climate conditions during the YD.

Terrestrial NP mass concentration ratios =====

Figure S4. Sharp Increases in Terrestrial Nanoparticle Element Ratios at the Onset of the Younger Dryas in Greenland Ice. Elemental mass concentration ratios (*e.g.*, total mass of concentration of nanoparticles containing one element divided by the mass of nanoparticles of another element) of predominantly terrestrial-associated nanoparticles in Greenland ice, measured using single-particle inductively coupled plasma time-of-flight mass spectrometry (SP-ICP-TOF-MS). Panels show (A) HREEs/LREEs (the heavy rare earth elements Gd through Lu compared to the light rare earth elements La through Sm), (B) Hf/Al, (C) Sb/Al, and (D) Zn/Al ratios, with normalization to aluminum, a standard lithogenic tracer. The shaded blue region denotes the Younger Dryas (YD) interval. All four panels display a sharp, well-defined peak near the onset of the YD (~5.32 m depth), marked by red asterisks. These elements are typically enriched in terrestrial sources and depleted in known extraterrestrial materials. The abrupt increase is therefore interpreted as a transient influx of continentally derived dust, consistent with deposition from a high-energy atmospheric airburst or impact event at the onset of the YD. Unlike broader climate-driven signals, the narrowness of these peaks supports a short-duration depositional pulse likely associated with the hypothesized Younger Dryas impact event.

Supporting Information, Tables

Supporting Information, Table S1. Distribution of impact-related proxies and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values across slope distance in the ice samples from Kangerlussuaq, Greenland. Shown are concentrations of nanodiamonds ($10^6/\text{mL}$), Fe- and Si-rich spherules ($\#/ \text{kg}$), carbon spherules ($\#/ \text{kg}$), shocked quartz ($\#/ \text{kg}$), meltglass ($\#/ \text{kg}$), microbreccia ($\#/ \text{kg}$), and glasslike carbon ($\#/ \text{kg}$), along with $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰) values spanning 2.90 to 8.50 m depth. Multiple proxies peak between 5.25 and 5.85 m, consistent with the onset of the Younger Dryas and indicative of high-temperature, high-energy processes such as airbursts or impact events.

$\delta^{18}\text{O}$		Nanodiamonds		Spherules, Fe and Si		Carbon Spherules	
Dist. (m)	‰	Dist. (m)	$10^6/\text{mL}$	Dist. (m)	$\#/ \text{kg}$	Dist. (m)	$\#/ \text{kg}$
2.90	-31.9	3.22	0.00000	3.67	12	3.22	0
3.10	-32.0	3.67	0.00679	4.27	0	3.67	0
3.30	-31.9	3.97	0.00000	5.17	0	4.27	0
3.50	-32.2	4.27	0.00000	5.32	0	5.02	0
3.90	-31.3	4.72	0.00000	5.48	34	5.17	100
4.10	-33.0	5.02	0.00054	5.63	14	5.32	560
4.30	-32.5	5.17	0.00529	5.78	0	5.48	640
4.50	-31.8	5.32	0.00052	6.23	8	5.63	360
4.70	-32.8	5.48	1414.73	6.98	0	5.78	320
4.90	-33.3	5.63	56.9830	7.43	5	5.93	280
5.10	-31.8	5.78	0.00012			6.08	160
5.30	-31.7	5.93	0.00069			6.23	160
5.50	-32.1	6.08	0.00113			6.38	0
5.70	-31.9	6.23	0.00063			6.98	0
5.90	-31.9	6.38	0.00117			7.43	0
6.10	-32.5	6.68	0.00000				
6.30	-31.9	6.98	0.00059				
6.50	-32.8	7.43	0.00008				
6.70	-33.8						
6.90	-33.0						
7.10	-32.9						
7.30	-31.8						
7.50	-32.1						
7.70	-33.5						
7.90	-33.5						
8.10	-32.0						
8.30	-32.3						
8.50	-33.7						

Meltglass		Shocked Quartz		Glasslike Carbon	
Dist. (m)	$\#/ \text{kg}$	Dist. (m)	$\#/ \text{kg}$	Depth (m)	$\#/ \text{kg}$
3.7	0	3.7	0	3.2	0
4.3	0	4.3	0	3.7	0
5.2	0.0	5.2	0	4.3	0
5.3	0.0	5.3	0	5.0	0
5.5	43.0	5.5	47	5.2	0
5.6	7.0	5.6	7	5.3	5
5.8	0.0	5.8	0	5.5	155
6.1	0	6.1	0	5.6	14
7.0	0	7.0	0	5.8	0
7.4	0	7.4	0	5.9	5

Microbreccia	
Dist. (m)	$\#/ \text{kg}$
3.7	0
4.3	0
5.2	0.0
5.3	0.0
5.5	68.0
5.6	14.0
5.8	0.0
6.1	0
7.0	0
7.4	0

Supporting Information, Table S2. Concentrations of selected trace elements in Greenland ice core samples by slope distance measured by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Elemental concentrations are reported in ng/L of ice for elements across slope distances ranging from 3.65 to 8.00 meters. With ICP-MS, the detection limits were too high to reveal meaningful changes in low-concentration elements such as the PGEs; nanoparticle analyses provided more meaningful results.

Mid (m)	Top (m)	Bot(m)	Platinum	Iridium	Ruthenium	Lithium	Vanadium	Chromium	Manganese	Cobalt
			Pt195(LR)	Ir #1 RUN	Ru101(LR)	Li7(LR)	V51(MR)	Cr52(MR)	Mn55(MR)	Co59(MR)
			ng/L	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L	ng/L
3.72	3.65	3.80	0.30	0.578	1.10	21704	59579	32923	292084	11279
3.87	3.80	3.95	0.28	0.362	0.92	17109	46116	26327	229251	8928
4.02	3.95	4.10	0.28	0.329	0.92	16654	45231	25775	224085	8634
4.17	4.10	4.25	0.22	0.318	0.89	17880	47345	27144	234823	9142
4.32	4.25	4.40	0.30	0.487	0.99	24914	63620	37199	320246	12229
4.47	4.40	4.55	0.22	0.314	0.92	31360	77064	45129	389904	14887
4.62	4.55	4.70	0.23	0.276	0.78	17423	47086	27238	233589	8795
4.77	4.70	4.85	0.51	0.781	0.68	10651	32726	19015	159968	5837
4.92	4.85	5.00	0.27	0.415	0.73	6184	18994	11082	92526	3465
5.07	5.00	5.15	0.35	0.378	0.71	9251	27821	16173	137395	5113
5.22	5.15	5.30	0.34	0.343	0.69	13606	40008	23153	196926	7261
5.37	5.30	5.45	0.28	0.446	0.72	19408	51092	29831	252130	9409
5.52	5.45	5.60	0.24	0.363	0.67	6352	24161	15576	112886	5555
5.67	5.60	5.75	0.31	0.446	0.72	6552	25122	16467	119383	5794
5.82	5.75	5.90	0.27	0.396	0.73	6656	25594	16674	124480	5980
5.98	5.90	6.05	0.42	0.467	0.74	6304	25403	16232	119825	5938
6.13	6.05	6.20	0.41	0.749	0.80	8779	34298	22668	161953	8327
6.28	6.20	6.35	0.41	0.578	0.76	8328	33708	21995	155983	7888
6.43	6.35	6.50	0.44	0.510	0.65	8614	33759	22804	161095	8433
6.58	6.50	6.65	0.36	0.583	0.58	7433	30678	20051	143836	7264
6.73	6.65	6.80	0.43	1.038	0.55	5040	22022	13964	105447	4875
6.88	6.80	6.95	0.35	0.697	0.53	5668	26379	16366	128701	6042
7.03	6.95	7.10	0.24	0.426	0.60	4980	25699	14591	121059	5207
7.18	7.10	7.25	0.46	0.494	0.68	10333	48780	27728	229976	10091
7.33	7.25	7.40	0.25	0.409	0.51	8100	39525	22458	185417	8418
7.48	7.40	7.55	0.34	0.397	0.58	9800	50617	30207	248123	10736
7.63	7.55	7.70	0.29	0.339	0.55	8217	44113	24124	207186	8693
7.78	7.70	7.85	0.34	0.377	0.43	6866	37469	20813	176226	7245
7.93	7.85	8.00	0.31	0.386	0.51	7600	37571	22135	179807	7519

Supporting Information, Table S2 (continued).

Mid(m)	Copper Cu63(MR) ng/L	Zinc Zn66(MR) ng/L	Titanium Ti47(MR) ng/L	Calcium Ca44(MR) ug/L	Magnesium Mg24(MR) ug/L	Potassium K39(HR) ug/L	Barium Ba138(LR) ug/L	Sodium Na23(MR) ug/L	Aluminum Al27(MR) ug/L	Iron Fe56(MR) ug/L
3.725	46363	52506	1015920	10106864	8034127	6125767	244835	5417883	19959506	22317373
3.875	37741	44806	788887	7998209	5992054	5290201	200326	4615999	15955480	17359680
4.025	37766	47800	780646	7318632	5870076	5049541	193166	4065417	15663003	17304122
4.175	40032	44329	820035	7446475	6245903	5231858	202188	4339852	16574454	18036976
4.325	55525	54434	1111488	9826924	8579036	6915632	263600	5347997	22079112	24890424
4.475	67790	74447	1344805	11295681	10832469	8279233	318292	5865550	25573220	30409006
4.625	38172	44837	804579	7396494	6153310	5291394	197181	4608612	17019644	18068946
4.775	24065	31534	523472	5836850	4188348	3709079	141659	3869873	12923849	12166346
4.925	15704	22261	303622	3526340	2371372	2243390	88208	2409815	7918334	7306193
5.075	22475	32020	448601	4800524	3466849	3182904	118788	3307588	11072880	10606760
5.225	35844	48237	650153	6484124	5036608	4420100	162820	4410632	14932357	15172148
5.375	43659	52436	888053	7790851	6854236	5636246	218896	4954120	19403358	19730784
5.525	18898	23447	923387	4381076	3006674	3628267	163489	2574789	11123994	9714767
5.675	19510	22351	965494	4539015	3034460	3460333	166477	2711579	11606937	10100837
5.825	21063	25350	980381	4637058	3102682	3746106	171194	2777244	12091630	10715670
5.975	20379	27897	960850	4863204	3048535	3641913	163870	2935673	12478026	10361321
6.125	27565	33414	1326017	6292565	4317215	4841741	218923	3640443	16857673	14298375
6.275	26649	34635	1280438	6048772	3963010	4512258	208454	3495027	16282764	14291651
6.425	28786	38752	1295200	6302333	4777883	4808012	213207	3582163	16672312	14476069
6.575	25937	33090	1139472	5672958	3728402	3998159	185522	3306052	15695898	12848363
6.725	16222	33031	768364	4351580	2498549	2757275	141225	2724514	11016972	8840646
6.875	22412	27141	944467	5552883	2922124	3347437	155197	2963211	13207676	10755585
7.025	17379	28775	891765	5525164	2731992	2886317	139011	3134903	13445304	9984124
7.175	33512	47839	1710120	9890706	5518194	5427387	239288	5105372	23225528	19304526
7.325	27796	44184	1367632	8167815	4326057	4547152	201823	4504793	19191853	15378351
7.475	37605	44828	1813470	11442568	5661295	6155068	240457	5950696	24864372	20782445
7.625	29043	44477	1460978	9918249	4616779	4567929	210453	5503965	21493699	16761122
7.775	24969	54991	1251303	8853021	3917894	4579530	191721	5237621	19865728	14435640
7.925	24478	69140	1280830	8927258	4175511	4448996	203207	5764025	19698401	14108094

Supporting Information, Table S2 (continued).

Mid (m)	Cadmium Cd111(LR) ng/L	Lanthanum La139(LR) ng/L	Cerium Ce140(LR) ng/L	Lead Pb208(LR) ng/L	Bismuth Bi209(LR) ng/L	Arsenic As75(HR)	Strontium Sr88(LR) ng/L	Cesium Cs133(LR) ng/L	Uranium U238(LR) ng/L	Praseodymium Pr141(LR) ng/L
3.725	64.74	28014	54759	3835	27.89	147.54	82689	619.95	561.54	6079
3.875	56.05	22245	42780	3216	25.61	142.39	69739	495.91	428.29	4785
4.025	57.83	21679	42216	3200	25.51	133.48	65013	495.55	415.95	4698
4.175	52.10	22710	43953	3298	25.37	135.35	68628	531.03	443.85	4945
4.325	67.76	31510	59757	4150	27.89	172.24	85651	722.57	590.06	6775
4.475	79.59	37506	73423	4966	25.09	184.12	93582	871.29	682.63	8325
4.625	50.11	19657	38405	3080	28.06	119.57	71761	501.15	360.50	4321
4.775	37.38	12662	23905	2237	23.41	85.02	61751	318.43	222.98	2763
4.925	28.49	8530	16577	1614	24.71	73.77	39482	195.71	128.19	1878
5.075	39.04	11148	21985	2143	28.84	118.47	50477	288.07	197.84	2549
5.225	56.32	16609	32138	3005	52.19	171.15	64260	414.72	308.92	3637
5.375	55.34	21364	41167	3486	30.79	144.89	76875	559.54	341.69	4638
5.525	35.23	19146	38436	2937	23.73	67.72	40838	410.36	378.58	4141
5.675	34.99	20452	41381	3073	23.08	74.65	43130	429.59	444.48	4514
5.825	38.05	20278	41041	3100	26.67	76.15	42551	443.78	396.42	4425
5.975	46.01	20574	41296	3317	40.53	81.73	46207	412.04	423.55	4503
6.125	48.92	28991	58235	4037	34.14	97.72	58088	551.00	577.91	6325
6.275	49.71	28709	56083	4171	37.56	109.01	57886	520.18	554.27	5954
6.425	60.58	30733	61812	4436	48.70	125.21	59098	527.33	579.10	6792
6.575	46.83	25740	52537	4009	44.58	126.41	55856	457.20	476.41	5741
6.725	52.24	18824	37407	3271	67.31	86.67	46544	324.84	298.61	4076
6.875	44.50	20664	43529	3278	44.12	115.51	52768	356.90	358.26	4811
7.025	41.63	20586	43762	3130	37.49	89.72	52907	313.27	293.76	4800
7.175	70.36	39258	81591	5307	55.32	146.49	80439	567.91	658.55	8877
7.325	70.94	30391	62766	4589	63.25	136.21	72913	470.70	449.99	6804
7.475	68.85	37304	78502	5081	46.72	150.14	88466	528.90	587.81	8726
7.625	71.51	32529	67617	4945	68.19	130.15	84569	432.52	429.86	7439
7.775	88.90	26832	55326	5390	114.52	152.71	78854	353.95	323.67	6199
7.925	119.61	26515	54524	5685	115.35	175.63	84582	355.39	288.78	5979

Supporting Information, Table S3. Lattice spacings for the four types of nanodiamonds observed at Kangerlussuaq. In crystallography, Miller-Bravais indices, expressed as hkl values, are a notational system used to describe the orientation of a family of planes of atoms as revealed by exposure to X-rays or an electron beam. The ‘d-spacing’ values are measured in Ångström between adjacent planes.

Cubic		n-Diamond		Lonsdaleite		i-Carbon	
hkl	d (Å)	hkl	d (Å)	hkl	d (Å)	hkl	d (Å)
111	2.06	111	2.06	100	2.18	110	3.04
220	1.26	200**	1.78	2	2.06	111	2.53
311	1.08	220	1.26	101	1.93	200	2.12
400	0.89	311	1.08	102	1.50	211	1.81
331	0.82	222**	1.04	110	1.26	220	1.54
422	0.73	400	0.89	103	1.16	311	1.30
551/333	0.69	331	0.82	200	1.09	400	1.10
440	0.63	420**	0.80	112	1.08	422	0.91
531	0.60	422	0.73	201	1.06	431	0.84
		511	0.69	202	0.97		

**Forbidden reflections

Supporting Information, Table S4. Total mass concentrations of nanoparticles (in g/g) in Greenland ice core samples measured by single-particle inductively coupled plasma time-of-flight mass spectrometry (SP-ICP-TOF-MS) for 45 selected elements across depth intervals from 3.67 to 6.53 meters, corresponding to the Holocene, Younger Dryas, and Bølling-Allerød periods. Two method blank controls (MB1, MB2) are included for comparison. These results allow the identification of anomalous elemental enrichment associated with climatic or impact-related events.

Mass Concentration	Total Mass of NPs							
Mid	Al	Si	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co
3.67	3.29E-03	6.81E-03	3.81E-04	5.97E-06	4.80E-06	3.62E-05	5.99E-03	1.60E-06
3.82	1.86E-03	3.75E-03	3.86E-04	4.53E-06	4.51E-06	3.47E-05	4.15E-03	5.61E-07
3.97	1.04E-03	1.60E-03	1.70E-04	1.90E-06	1.34E-06	1.51E-05	2.33E-03	3.61E-07
4.12	4.23E-03	5.83E-03	6.57E-04	7.31E-06	1.32E-05	5.22E-05	9.30E-03	1.28E-06
4.27	1.85E-03	2.97E-03	2.47E-04	3.18E-06	3.15E-06	2.19E-05	3.69E-03	5.90E-07
4.42	2.13E-03	4.20E-03	4.04E-04	5.15E-06	6.19E-06	3.73E-05	4.58E-03	7.52E-07
4.57	2.30E-03	4.65E-03	3.74E-04	4.91E-06	4.69E-06	2.80E-05	3.86E-03	6.48E-07
4.72	3.08E-03	4.31E-03	4.75E-04	5.21E-06	5.55E-06	3.73E-05	6.25E-03	1.03E-06
4.87	2.36E-03	3.47E-03	3.96E-04	4.41E-06	4.09E-06	3.34E-05	4.89E-03	7.77E-07
5.02	3.09E-03	4.95E-03	5.28E-04	5.86E-06	5.28E-06	4.88E-05	6.37E-03	8.91E-07
5.17	4.52E-04	8.61E-04	7.27E-05	1.17E-06	1.19E-06	6.53E-06	9.84E-04	2.20E-07
5.32	4.90E-03	2.08E-02	5.72E-04	1.04E-05	7.29E-06	6.84E-05	8.61E-03	2.14E-06
5.48	3.06E-03	1.50E-02	4.14E-04	7.85E-06	5.97E-06	4.66E-05	5.64E-03	1.30E-06
5.63	6.72E-03	2.60E-02	1.68E-03	1.56E-05	9.04E-06	9.77E-05	1.27E-02	2.69E-06
5.78	6.93E-03	2.42E-02	7.64E-04	1.31E-05	1.01E-05	1.11E-04	1.24E-02	3.42E-06
5.93	4.74E-03	2.05E-02	6.19E-04	9.69E-06	7.80E-06	6.38E-05	9.21E-03	1.92E-06
6.08	1.79E-03	7.35E-03	1.99E-04	3.65E-06	2.54E-06	2.24E-05	3.39E-03	8.88E-07
6.23	4.03E-03	2.47E-02	5.45E-04	1.14E-05	7.64E-06	7.24E-05	7.88E-03	1.95E-06
6.38	2.00E-03	1.36E-02	2.22E-04	5.27E-06	7.04E-06	2.85E-05	3.64E-03	1.16E-06
6.53	1.57E-03	1.09E-02	2.10E-04	3.87E-06	3.32E-06	2.64E-05	3.09E-03	7.95E-07
MB1	7.70E-13	3.51E-11	5.36E-14	7.62E-14	6.31E-14	4.15E-14	4.02E-13	4.04E-14
MB2	7.21E-13	2.42E-11	6.17E-14	8.39E-14	4.75E-14	4.66E-14	6.13E-13	2.88E-14

Supporting Information, Table S4 (continued).

Mass Concentration			Total Mass of NPs					
Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Zr	Nb	Ru	Rh	Pd
5.31E-06	4.48E-06	5.36E-06	9.88E-06	3.17E-06	1.07E-06	2.22E-06	5.57E-07	2.55E-06
1.38E-06	1.10E-06	1.50E-06	2.29E-06	5.37E-06	2.56E-07	2.19E-07	6.14E-08	4.41E-07
9.92E-07	7.25E-07	8.94E-07	1.42E-06	8.17E-07	1.53E-07	2.43E-07	6.95E-08	2.99E-07
4.50E-06	3.09E-06	3.77E-06	7.68E-06	8.21E-06	5.81E-07	1.67E-06	3.56E-07	1.95E-06
1.65E-06	1.25E-06	1.72E-06	3.10E-06	1.64E-06	3.00E-07	5.20E-07	1.25E-07	7.34E-07
2.67E-06	1.11E-06	2.23E-06	2.68E-06	1.88E-06	2.24E-07	2.54E-07	6.98E-08	3.47E-07
1.68E-06	1.37E-06	2.48E-06	2.47E-06	4.70E-06	4.96E-07	3.22E-07	8.82E-08	5.68E-07
3.57E-06	2.45E-06	2.83E-06	5.67E-06	4.11E-06	4.34E-07	9.44E-07	2.21E-07	1.57E-06
2.02E-06	1.84E-06	2.55E-06	3.79E-06	3.42E-06	3.42E-07	6.98E-07	1.61E-07	1.03E-06
2.40E-06	1.91E-06	2.30E-06	4.21E-06	5.13E-06	3.87E-07	5.18E-07	1.56E-07	8.27E-07
8.38E-07	6.55E-07	1.20E-06	2.01E-06	8.24E-07	1.88E-07	3.64E-07	9.16E-08	4.81E-07
4.88E-06	4.12E-06	5.31E-06	5.36E-06	2.52E-06	6.43E-07	8.16E-07	2.27E-07	1.08E-06
2.39E-06	1.53E-06	2.20E-06	1.85E-06	4.24E-06	3.42E-07	2.24E-07	5.08E-08	4.71E-07
7.10E-06	5.43E-06	7.89E-06	8.77E-06	2.99E-06	9.27E-07	1.30E-06	3.20E-07	1.53E-06
9.10E-06	7.90E-06	1.31E-05	1.93E-05	5.31E-06	1.67E-06	4.01E-06	9.61E-07	4.46E-06
5.24E-06	4.36E-06	4.91E-06	6.50E-06	4.25E-06	7.14E-07	8.88E-07	2.39E-07	1.15E-06
2.39E-06	1.65E-06	2.63E-06	3.93E-06	1.45E-05	3.93E-07	6.67E-07	1.84E-07	1.90E-06
4.27E-06	2.63E-06	3.94E-06	3.66E-06	6.61E-06	4.11E-07	4.49E-07	1.14E-07	7.07E-07
4.36E-06	2.47E-06	3.03E-06	3.57E-06	6.28E-07	3.03E-07	5.95E-07	1.44E-07	6.42E-07
2.07E-06	1.35E-06	2.07E-06	2.15E-06	1.04E-06	2.09E-07	3.38E-07	9.47E-08	4.41E-07
1.57E-13	1.46E-13	1.59E-13	4.93E-13	8.42E-14	3.92E-14	7.84E-14	2.02E-14	9.67E-14
1.56E-13	1.10E-13	2.98E-13	4.27E-13	7.35E-14	2.98E-14	8.26E-14	1.98E-14	1.08E-13

Supporting Information, Table S4 (continued).

Mass Concentration			Total Mass of NPs					
Sn	Sb	Ba	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu
1.73E-06	1.68E-06	4.30E-05	1.47E-06	3.58E-06	5.75E-07	2.30E-06	1.45E-06	6.32E-07
2.05E-07	1.71E-07	4.20E-05	2.77E-06	6.31E-06	5.04E-07	1.47E-06	2.52E-07	9.29E-08
2.44E-07	2.21E-07	1.80E-05	5.78E-07	1.46E-06	1.35E-07	4.95E-07	1.66E-07	7.68E-08
1.43E-06	1.09E-06	7.06E-05	2.95E-06	9.08E-06	8.18E-07	2.67E-06	8.89E-07	4.21E-07
4.91E-07	4.81E-07	2.73E-05	6.52E-07	1.72E-06	1.86E-07	7.87E-07	3.52E-07	1.87E-07
2.97E-07	2.04E-07	4.37E-05	3.58E-06	7.65E-06	6.29E-07	1.97E-06	3.12E-07	1.18E-07
2.91E-07	2.96E-07	3.29E-05	2.09E-06	4.86E-06	3.97E-07	1.40E-06	3.55E-07	1.19E-07
1.06E-06	1.10E-06	4.96E-05	2.32E-06	4.91E-06	5.09E-07	2.00E-06	8.01E-07	3.52E-07
5.23E-07	4.31E-07	4.11E-05	1.59E-06	4.04E-06	3.75E-07	1.33E-06	5.14E-07	2.25E-07
6.37E-07	4.53E-07	6.34E-05	2.81E-06	6.80E-06	4.99E-07	1.68E-06	3.91E-07	1.61E-07
3.56E-07	4.01E-07	7.96E-06	4.09E-07	1.15E-06	1.38E-07	5.58E-07	2.68E-07	1.34E-07
8.88E-07	8.46E-07	6.49E-05	1.22E-06	4.18E-06	3.90E-07	1.34E-06	6.49E-07	2.93E-07
2.26E-07	8.44E-07	4.30E-05	1.48E-06	3.80E-06	3.26E-07	1.06E-06	2.29E-07	8.44E-08
1.83E-06	9.07E-07	8.44E-05	2.69E-06	7.32E-06	6.68E-07	2.47E-06	1.01E-06	4.66E-07
3.29E-06	3.10E-06	9.32E-05	2.97E-06	8.14E-06	1.26E-06	5.59E-06	2.49E-06	1.35E-06
9.84E-07	8.48E-07	6.56E-05	2.33E-06	5.15E-06	4.89E-07	2.03E-06	8.04E-07	3.13E-07
6.83E-07	6.23E-07	2.17E-05	9.79E-07	2.13E-06	2.78E-07	1.22E-06	5.65E-07	2.65E-07
5.56E-07	3.30E-07	5.74E-05	1.86E-06	5.10E-06	4.14E-07	1.33E-06	3.65E-07	1.65E-07
8.33E-07	5.74E-07	2.33E-05	4.06E-07	1.20E-06	1.97E-07	7.58E-07	4.59E-07	2.12E-07
4.84E-06	2.86E-07	2.19E-05	5.08E-07	1.51E-06	1.35E-07	5.93E-07	2.58E-07	1.38E-07
8.29E-14	6.65E-14	2.86E-14	2.51E-14	2.46E-14	1.75E-14	9.43E-14	5.88E-14	3.46E-14
7.42E-14	5.49E-14	2.40E-14	1.88E-14	2.32E-14	1.57E-14	9.56E-14	5.61E-14	2.98E-14

Supporting Information, Table S4 (continued).

Mass Concentration			Total Mass of NPs					
Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu	Hf
1.82E-06	3.72E-07	1.26E-06	3.42E-07	1.03E-06	3.47E-07	1.00E-06	3.21E-07	1.39E-06
2.79E-07	5.79E-08	1.43E-07	3.88E-08	1.14E-07	3.58E-08	1.18E-07	3.16E-08	2.27E-07
2.17E-07	4.67E-08	1.41E-07	4.47E-08	1.22E-07	4.90E-08	1.62E-07	3.55E-08	1.99E-07
1.14E-06	2.38E-07	7.55E-07	2.23E-07	6.67E-07	2.22E-07	7.33E-07	2.31E-07	9.30E-07
4.21E-07	9.17E-08	3.24E-07	9.59E-08	2.51E-07	8.63E-08	3.01E-07	8.50E-08	4.41E-07
3.95E-07	7.86E-08	2.33E-07	6.39E-08	2.15E-07	6.16E-08	2.41E-07	6.17E-08	2.29E-07
4.09E-07	6.68E-08	2.35E-07	6.31E-08	1.98E-07	5.96E-08	1.82E-07	4.62E-08	2.57E-07
9.10E-07	1.71E-07	6.27E-07	1.79E-07	6.11E-07	1.83E-07	6.41E-07	1.63E-07	6.89E-07
4.53E-07	1.19E-07	3.51E-07	1.03E-07	3.40E-07	1.08E-07	3.12E-07	9.35E-08	4.31E-07
4.64E-07	1.11E-07	3.52E-07	9.18E-08	2.86E-07	9.79E-08	3.02E-07	8.98E-08	4.52E-07
3.36E-07	6.76E-08	2.17E-07	5.39E-08	2.01E-07	7.18E-08	2.02E-07	5.42E-08	2.89E-07
7.70E-07	1.55E-07	4.95E-07	1.56E-07	5.11E-07	1.44E-07	4.94E-07	1.36E-07	5.82E-07
2.89E-07	4.79E-08	1.47E-07	4.35E-08	1.18E-07	3.73E-08	1.39E-07	3.67E-08	1.64E-07
9.22E-07	2.63E-07	7.01E-07	2.07E-07	6.90E-07	2.33E-07	5.86E-07	1.87E-07	9.30E-07
3.44E-06	6.37E-07	2.52E-06	6.56E-07	1.86E-06	6.73E-07	2.10E-06	6.66E-07	2.43E-06
1.00E-06	1.86E-07	5.57E-07	1.81E-07	5.36E-07	1.62E-07	5.13E-07	1.88E-07	7.32E-07
6.65E-07	1.28E-07	3.54E-07	1.54E-07	3.94E-07	1.26E-07	3.70E-07	1.01E-07	6.08E-07
4.10E-07	8.39E-08	2.83E-07	7.46E-08	2.09E-07	7.52E-08	2.28E-07	6.41E-08	3.59E-07
5.49E-07	1.03E-07	3.82E-07	1.21E-07	3.29E-07	1.20E-07	3.67E-07	1.10E-07	4.07E-07
2.92E-07	6.56E-08	2.16E-07	6.05E-08	1.81E-07	6.67E-08	1.99E-07	5.43E-08	2.63E-07
7.35E-14	1.73E-14	4.49E-14	1.56E-14	5.16E-14	1.58E-14	4.92E-14	1.54E-14	6.90E-14
6.27E-14	1.47E-14	5.05E-14	1.49E-14	3.96E-14	1.35E-14	4.00E-14	1.43E-14	5.21E-14

Supporting Information, Table S4 (continued).

Mass Concentration		Total Mass of NPs							
Ta	W	Re	Os	Ir	Pt	Au	Pb	Th	U
7.73E-07	2.33E-06	7.79E-07	8.38E-07	9.01E-07	2.40E-06	1.49E-06	1.27E-06	8.59E-07	6.15E-07
9.80E-08	2.34E-07	7.58E-08	9.39E-08	1.25E-07	2.38E-07	1.89E-07	2.25E-07	6.33E-07	1.62E-07
1.15E-07	2.53E-07	9.00E-08	1.10E-07	1.22E-07	2.78E-07	2.11E-07	1.34E-07	1.38E-07	8.16E-08
5.09E-07	1.46E-06	4.88E-07	5.78E-07	6.05E-07	1.57E-06	9.07E-07	8.33E-07	7.56E-07	4.00E-07
1.78E-07	5.29E-07	1.91E-07	2.09E-07	2.43E-07	5.79E-07	3.61E-07	3.16E-07	2.35E-07	1.52E-07
1.25E-07	3.20E-07	1.10E-07	1.23E-07	1.30E-07	3.08E-07	2.16E-07	2.57E-07	5.68E-07	1.12E-07
1.30E-07	3.10E-07	1.15E-07	1.38E-07	1.61E-07	4.26E-07	2.33E-07	4.44E-07	5.49E-07	1.59E-07
3.92E-07	9.52E-07	3.84E-07	4.18E-07	4.92E-07	1.16E-06	7.65E-07	7.42E-07	4.69E-07	2.93E-07
2.47E-07	6.23E-07	2.23E-07	2.56E-07	2.97E-07	7.39E-07	4.58E-07	4.13E-07	5.87E-07	1.79E-07
2.26E-07	6.08E-07	1.90E-07	2.29E-07	2.78E-07	5.83E-07	4.29E-07	5.02E-07	1.56E-06	1.94E-07
1.62E-07	3.96E-07	1.32E-07	1.53E-07	1.86E-07	3.74E-07	2.70E-07	1.85E-07	1.47E-07	9.80E-08
5.64E-07	9.87E-07	3.20E-07	3.53E-07	3.91E-07	1.12E-06	4.97E-07	8.65E-07	4.12E-07	2.57E-07
1.33E-07	3.11E-07	8.15E-08	9.45E-08	1.17E-07	2.89E-07	1.50E-07	3.98E-07	2.58E-07	1.09E-07
7.53E-07	1.71E-06	4.53E-07	5.20E-07	6.51E-07	1.50E-06	8.07E-07	1.02E-06	6.41E-07	4.24E-07
2.01E-06	4.44E-06	1.32E-06	1.42E-06	1.61E-06	5.35E-06	2.51E-06	2.14E-06	1.28E-06	1.02E-06
5.81E-07	1.13E-06	3.55E-07	4.25E-07	4.87E-07	1.09E-06	5.68E-07	7.72E-07	5.56E-07	2.91E-07
4.45E-07	7.83E-07	2.41E-07	3.19E-07	3.02E-07	9.06E-07	3.88E-07	4.13E-07	3.56E-07	2.30E-07
2.62E-07	4.61E-07	1.36E-07	1.68E-07	1.96E-07	4.94E-07	2.10E-07	4.86E-07	5.27E-07	1.31E-07
3.61E-07	7.24E-07	2.00E-07	2.19E-07	2.98E-07	7.13E-07	3.43E-07	4.67E-07	2.64E-07	1.84E-07
2.16E-07	4.16E-07	1.18E-07	1.58E-07	1.73E-07	4.71E-07	2.77E-07	3.00E-07	1.61E-07	1.12E-07
5.96E-14	1.01E-13	2.70E-14	3.40E-14	3.95E-14	1.12E-13	6.35E-14	3.95E-14	3.05E-14	2.76E-14
3.10E-14	1.14E-13	2.87E-14	3.71E-14	4.47E-14	8.69E-14	7.14E-14	3.88E-14	2.62E-14	2.26E-14

Supporting Information, Table S5. Total number concentrations of nanoparticles in Greenland ice core samples measured by single-particle inductively coupled plasma time-of-flight mass spectrometry (SP-ICP-TOF-MS). The table presents total numbers of nanoparticles for 45 selected elements across depth intervals from 3.67 to 6.53 meters, corresponding to the Holocene, Younger Dryas, and Bølling-Allerød periods. Two method blank controls (MB1, MB2) are included for comparison. These values represent the total nanoparticulate number concentrations for each stratigraphic level, allowing for the identification of anomalous elemental enrichment associated with climatic or impact-related events.

Number Concentration		Total Number of NPs						
Mid	Al	Si	Ti	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co
3.7	1.25E+11	1.02E+10	8.68E+10	5.93E+09	4.79E+09	2.76E+10	5.09E+11	3.56E+09
3.8	2.29E+10	4.72E+09	2.73E+10	3.21E+09	2.60E+09	1.43E+10	4.39E+10	1.13E+09
4.0	2.81E+10	2.52E+09	2.61E+10	1.65E+09	1.17E+09	9.63E+09	8.07E+10	7.78E+08
4.1	1.18E+11	9.43E+09	1.09E+11	6.70E+09	5.74E+09	3.91E+10	3.41E+11	2.90E+09
4.3	5.41E+10	4.72E+09	4.23E+10	2.90E+09	2.19E+09	1.63E+10	1.64E+11	1.40E+09
4.4	2.80E+10	5.36E+09	3.19E+10	3.62E+09	3.06E+09	1.56E+10	5.44E+10	1.35E+09
4.6	3.40E+10	5.54E+09	3.24E+10	3.13E+09	2.44E+09	1.27E+10	6.96E+10	1.21E+09
4.7	7.92E+10	6.74E+09	7.11E+10	4.54E+09	4.17E+09	2.64E+10	2.14E+11	2.37E+09
4.9	4.93E+10	5.37E+09	4.70E+10	3.41E+09	3.01E+09	1.76E+10	1.16E+11	1.62E+09
5.0	4.59E+10	7.17E+09	4.64E+10	4.21E+09	4.11E+09	2.35E+10	8.92E+10	1.80E+09
5.2	1.87E+10	1.36E+09	1.43E+10	8.43E+08	8.25E+08	4.54E+09	7.50E+10	4.69E+08
5.3	1.04E+11	1.64E+10	7.80E+10	6.71E+09	5.09E+09	3.22E+10	3.02E+11	3.84E+09
5.5	3.75E+10	1.03E+10	3.48E+10	4.30E+09	3.16E+09	1.64E+10	7.75E+10	2.00E+09
5.6	1.40E+11	2.31E+10	1.34E+11	9.07E+09	6.80E+09	4.28E+10	3.91E+11	4.64E+09
5.8	2.17E+11	2.29E+10	1.56E+11	9.86E+09	9.07E+09	5.68E+10	8.62E+11	6.40E+09
5.9	9.68E+10	1.58E+10	8.41E+10	6.17E+09	4.98E+09	3.24E+10	2.65E+11	3.47E+09
6.1	5.16E+10	5.92E+09	3.82E+10	2.43E+09	2.19E+09	1.40E+10	1.83E+11	1.64E+09
6.2	4.67E+10	1.55E+10	4.71E+10	5.21E+09	4.31E+09	2.40E+10	9.18E+10	2.75E+09
6.4	4.66E+10	8.38E+09	3.37E+10	2.72E+09	2.38E+09	1.41E+10	1.48E+11	1.74E+09
6.5	3.18E+10	7.29E+09	2.58E+10	1.84E+09	1.68E+09	1.11E+10	9.34E+10	1.26E+09
MB1	409	337	193	365	413	393	622	413
MB2	427	290	253	377	315	452	996	328

Supporting Information, Table S5 (continued).

Number Concentration Total Number of NPs

Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Zr	Nb	Ru	Rh	Pd
3.06E+09	3.30E+09	2.92E+09	3.94E+09	3.80E+09	4.36E+09	3.40E+09	3.46E+09	3.16E+09
6.18E+08	6.97E+08	6.89E+08	8.75E+08	9.80E+08	6.24E+08	3.35E+08	3.92E+08	3.94E+08
5.56E+08	5.46E+08	4.32E+08	5.49E+08	5.03E+08	4.85E+08	3.70E+08	4.26E+08	3.55E+08
2.57E+09	2.36E+09	1.90E+09	2.98E+09	2.94E+09	2.20E+09	2.57E+09	2.25E+09	2.11E+09
1.01E+09	9.58E+08	9.27E+08	1.22E+09	8.78E+08	1.01E+09	7.93E+08	7.75E+08	8.91E+08
9.30E+08	6.50E+08	8.36E+08	1.02E+09	1.05E+09	6.91E+08	3.93E+08	4.21E+08	3.90E+08
8.43E+08	8.01E+08	8.21E+08	9.52E+08	1.45E+09	1.05E+09	4.84E+08	5.48E+08	6.03E+08
1.75E+09	1.74E+09	1.19E+09	2.20E+09	1.98E+09	1.55E+09	1.35E+09	1.37E+09	1.79E+09
1.06E+09	1.22E+09	9.31E+08	1.46E+09	1.47E+09	1.18E+09	1.05E+09	9.98E+08	1.05E+09
1.03E+09	1.27E+09	9.17E+08	1.61E+09	1.52E+09	1.24E+09	7.65E+08	9.46E+08	8.53E+08
4.39E+08	4.98E+08	6.07E+08	7.56E+08	6.54E+08	6.28E+08	5.48E+08	5.59E+08	5.56E+08
2.33E+09	2.30E+09	2.21E+09	2.00E+09	1.66E+09	2.02E+09	1.29E+09	1.49E+09	1.38E+09
1.04E+09	8.94E+08	6.78E+08	6.75E+08	5.55E+08	6.56E+08	3.42E+08	3.31E+08	3.74E+08
3.29E+09	3.41E+09	2.62E+09	3.31E+09	2.46E+09	2.81E+09	1.99E+09	2.07E+09	1.99E+09
5.02E+09	5.81E+09	5.43E+09	7.15E+09	6.73E+09	6.23E+09	6.19E+09	6.35E+09	5.68E+09
2.45E+09	2.28E+09	2.06E+09	2.41E+09	1.97E+09	2.16E+09	1.37E+09	1.54E+09	1.42E+09
1.32E+09	1.18E+09	1.17E+09	1.47E+09	1.06E+09	1.28E+09	1.01E+09	1.17E+09	1.17E+09
1.76E+09	1.45E+09	1.52E+09	1.31E+09	9.22E+08	9.38E+08	7.03E+08	7.31E+08	6.20E+08
1.33E+09	1.38E+09	1.18E+09	1.31E+09	9.74E+08	1.02E+09	9.04E+08	9.10E+08	8.22E+08
8.97E+08	9.10E+08	8.59E+08	7.70E+08	6.77E+08	6.66E+08	5.15E+08	6.22E+08	5.33E+08
401	473	413	746	582	602	486	522	506
427	390	373	651	535	519	519	514	543

Supporting Information, Table S5 (continued).

Number Concentration Total Number of NPs

Sn	Sb	Ba	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu
3.30E+09	3.54E+09	7.00E+10	5.19E+09	8.88E+09	4.31E+09	3.80E+09	4.17E+09	3.75E+09
3.83E+08	3.75E+08	2.56E+10	4.02E+09	6.64E+09	1.53E+09	9.75E+08	5.51E+08	5.08E+08
4.51E+08	4.78E+08	2.33E+10	1.41E+09	2.61E+09	7.62E+08	6.20E+08	4.51E+08	4.54E+08
2.58E+09	2.31E+09	1.01E+11	7.16E+09	1.23E+10	3.94E+09	3.05E+09	2.41E+09	2.49E+09
9.27E+08	1.02E+09	3.81E+10	2.40E+09	3.98E+09	1.34E+09	1.19E+09	1.01E+09	1.10E+09
5.40E+08	4.34E+08	3.10E+10	4.23E+09	6.90E+09	1.59E+09	1.24E+09	6.16E+08	6.28E+08
5.35E+08	6.22E+08	2.84E+10	3.30E+09	5.95E+09	1.34E+09	1.05E+09	7.60E+08	6.15E+08
1.67E+09	1.95E+09	6.32E+10	4.53E+09	7.58E+09	2.68E+09	2.46E+09	2.07E+09	1.96E+09
9.81E+08	9.25E+08	4.29E+10	3.12E+09	5.60E+09	1.81E+09	1.44E+09	1.30E+09	1.24E+09
1.03E+09	9.12E+08	4.59E+10	5.92E+09	1.01E+10	2.20E+09	1.70E+09	9.56E+08	9.07E+08
6.32E+08	6.54E+08	1.27E+10	1.12E+09	1.36E+09	7.05E+08	7.48E+08	7.30E+08	7.59E+08
1.56E+09	1.70E+09	6.67E+10	4.08E+09	8.45E+09	2.58E+09	1.94E+09	1.76E+09	1.60E+09
4.13E+08	4.10E+08	3.07E+10	1.96E+09	4.12E+09	9.05E+08	7.00E+08	4.73E+08	4.21E+08
2.08E+09	1.84E+09	9.62E+10	6.81E+09	1.29E+10	3.53E+09	3.13E+09	2.68E+09	2.58E+09
5.81E+09	6.44E+09	1.36E+11	1.16E+10	1.66E+10	9.11E+09	8.40E+09	6.73E+09	7.65E+09
1.71E+09	1.70E+09	7.46E+10	5.49E+09	1.00E+10	2.61E+09	2.34E+09	2.08E+09	1.81E+09
1.22E+09	1.24E+09	3.44E+10	2.32E+09	3.94E+09	1.64E+09	1.56E+09	1.45E+09	1.44E+09
7.31E+08	6.60E+08	4.29E+10	3.67E+09	6.93E+09	1.79E+09	1.34E+09	8.82E+08	8.98E+08
1.23E+09	1.10E+09	2.85E+10	1.83E+09	3.38E+09	1.54E+09	1.18E+09	1.22E+09	1.20E+09
5.67E+08	5.70E+08	2.28E+10	1.58E+09	2.91E+09	8.38E+08	7.94E+08	7.01E+08	7.39E+08
598	542	710	782	682	630	634	642	746
581	502	589	630	709	618	713	655	709

Supporting Information, Table S5 (continued).

Number Concentration Total Number of NPs

Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu	Hf
4.60E+09	4.07E+09	4.28E+09	3.96E+09	3.83E+09	3.96E+09	3.75E+09	4.17E+09	4.39E+09
5.43E+08	5.83E+08	4.62E+08	4.37E+08	4.29E+08	4.19E+08	4.32E+08	4.05E+08	5.40E+08
5.15E+08	5.37E+08	4.81E+08	4.97E+08	4.57E+08	5.52E+08	5.96E+08	4.63E+08	5.96E+08
2.70E+09	2.54E+09	2.63E+09	2.52E+09	2.47E+09	2.52E+09	2.81E+09	3.00E+09	2.70E+09
1.05E+09	1.06E+09	1.09E+09	1.10E+09	9.21E+08	9.94E+08	1.10E+09	1.09E+09	1.32E+09
6.66E+08	7.16E+08	5.66E+08	5.40E+08	5.69E+08	5.50E+08	5.62E+08	6.10E+08	6.69E+08
8.21E+08	6.80E+08	6.86E+08	6.70E+08	6.92E+08	6.48E+08	6.38E+08	5.67E+08	6.89E+08
2.11E+09	1.86E+09	2.06E+09	2.01E+09	2.28E+09	2.10E+09	2.36E+09	2.07E+09	2.01E+09
1.06E+09	1.28E+09	1.17E+09	1.15E+09	1.24E+09	1.19E+09	1.14E+09	1.18E+09	1.26E+09
1.03E+09	1.22E+09	1.13E+09	9.86E+08	1.02E+09	1.10E+09	1.07E+09	1.11E+09	1.15E+09
8.17E+08	7.30E+08	7.48E+08	6.14E+08	7.34E+08	7.70E+08	7.48E+08	6.72E+08	8.43E+08
1.87E+09	1.64E+09	1.65E+09	1.74E+09	1.80E+09	1.59E+09	1.78E+09	1.70E+09	1.77E+09
5.60E+08	4.26E+08	4.40E+08	4.65E+08	4.15E+08	4.13E+08	4.95E+08	4.51E+08	4.29E+08
2.19E+09	2.73E+09	2.40E+09	2.34E+09	2.47E+09	2.59E+09	2.16E+09	2.28E+09	2.73E+09
8.28E+09	7.19E+09	8.28E+09	6.94E+09	6.85E+09	7.52E+09	7.73E+09	8.32E+09	7.15E+09
2.33E+09	2.08E+09	1.81E+09	1.98E+09	1.90E+09	1.84E+09	1.89E+09	2.33E+09	2.09E+09
1.56E+09	1.38E+09	1.17E+09	1.65E+09	1.39E+09	1.39E+09	1.30E+09	1.26E+09	1.50E+09
9.22E+08	8.94E+08	9.14E+08	8.07E+08	7.63E+08	8.14E+08	8.22E+08	7.67E+08	9.14E+08
1.32E+09	1.14E+09	1.24E+09	1.28E+09	1.15E+09	1.30E+09	1.31E+09	1.35E+09	1.16E+09
7.01E+08	6.84E+08	6.77E+08	6.53E+08	6.60E+08	7.28E+08	7.28E+08	6.70E+08	7.21E+08
734	778	586	682	750	674	730	742	827
647	668	726	713	614	651	614	767	651

Supporting Information, Table S5 (continued).

Number Concentration Total Number of NPs

Ta	W	Re	Os	Ir	Pt	Au	Pb	Th	U
3.54E+09	4.15E+09	4.71E+09	3.78E+09	3.78E+09	4.07E+09	4.25E+09	5.16E+09	4.52E+09	4.92E+09
4.46E+08	4.13E+08	4.51E+08	4.19E+08	5.27E+08	4.16E+08	5.16E+08	7.26E+08	1.27E+09	5.51E+08
5.09E+08	4.63E+08	5.31E+08	4.72E+08	5.12E+08	4.69E+08	5.77E+08	5.59E+08	6.88E+08	6.33E+08
2.36E+09	2.58E+09	2.82E+09	2.60E+09	2.58E+09	2.58E+09	2.49E+09	3.59E+09	3.49E+09	3.06E+09
8.05E+08	9.39E+08	1.09E+09	9.39E+08	1.02E+09	9.88E+08	9.64E+08	1.35E+09	1.42E+09	1.21E+09
5.37E+08	5.66E+08	6.38E+08	5.44E+08	5.59E+08	5.28E+08	5.88E+08	9.21E+08	1.46E+09	6.50E+08
5.74E+08	5.35E+08	6.76E+08	6.06E+08	6.73E+08	7.15E+08	6.22E+08	1.28E+09	1.46E+09	8.66E+08
1.74E+09	1.70E+09	2.20E+09	1.81E+09	2.06E+09	1.98E+09	2.06E+09	2.59E+09	2.72E+09	2.28E+09
1.06E+09	1.09E+09	1.27E+09	1.09E+09	1.23E+09	1.24E+09	1.22E+09	1.51E+09	1.86E+09	1.40E+09
9.95E+08	1.02E+09	1.07E+09	9.76E+08	1.14E+09	9.90E+08	1.13E+09	1.51E+09	2.09E+09	1.20E+09
7.05E+08	6.61E+08	7.56E+08	6.61E+08	7.52E+08	6.07E+08	7.41E+08	7.70E+08	8.86E+08	7.52E+08
1.82E+09	1.69E+09	1.88E+09	1.71E+09	1.73E+09	1.93E+09	1.24E+09	2.94E+09	2.32E+09	1.93E+09
4.07E+08	5.19E+08	4.76E+08	4.65E+08	5.06E+08	4.92E+08	3.85E+08	1.20E+09	7.95E+08	6.20E+08
2.44E+09	2.81E+09	2.71E+09	2.56E+09	2.93E+09	2.52E+09	2.04E+09	3.79E+09	3.10E+09	3.04E+09
6.23E+09	7.36E+09	7.77E+09	6.94E+09	6.98E+09	9.24E+09	6.44E+09	9.11E+09	8.23E+09	7.86E+09
1.85E+09	1.86E+09	2.11E+09	2.13E+09	2.16E+09	1.86E+09	1.42E+09	2.89E+09	2.82E+09	2.07E+09
1.41E+09	1.32E+09	1.40E+09	1.54E+09	1.32E+09	1.58E+09	9.49E+08	1.64E+09	1.72E+09	1.75E+09
8.22E+08	7.79E+08	8.10E+08	8.18E+08	8.38E+08	8.50E+08	5.24E+08	1.54E+09	1.41E+09	9.02E+08
1.15E+09	1.21E+09	1.16E+09	1.07E+09	1.28E+09	1.22E+09	8.52E+08	1.81E+09	1.51E+09	1.38E+09
6.60E+08	6.87E+08	6.97E+08	7.49E+08	7.35E+08	8.04E+08	6.12E+08	9.86E+08	8.90E+08	8.38E+08
778	678	630	658	706	778	706	710	811	859
581	842	684	701	772	606	776	730	747	718

Text S1. Modeling Parameters from the Earth Impact Effects Program (EIEP)

We used the EIEP[1, 2] to derive first-order estimates of transient crater dimensions, shock pressures, thermal radiation, and ejecta dispersal patterns based on defined input parameters.

Comet diameter = 1000 m

Density, start = 500 kg/m³

Breakup = 250 kg/m³, SL-7 = 0.25g/cm³

Expands to 1270 m

Impactor velocity = 30 km/s = 30000 mm/ms

Entry angle = 45°

Target density = 1000 kg/m³; ice

Energy, Mt, atmos = 28100 Mt

Impact energy = 1.03e20 joules

Impact energy = 24500 Mt

Initial breakup = 100 km

Airburst altitude = none, forms a crater

Residual velocity at surface = 28 km/s = 28000 mm/ms

Angular velocity x = 19798 mm/ms

Angular velocity y = -19798 mm/ms

Transient crater in ice = 11.6 km

Hits as an ellipse 2.47 x 1.74 km

Final crater = 167 m

Richter scale = 3.2 at 0.1 km

Wind velocity = 442 km/s

Breccia layer 3 m

Impact recurrence = 290,000 years

Shear = 750 kPa

Yield stress = 500 kPa

Ground, 75m, units from top = 253-(75/750 x 253) = 228 units

Grid: DX: 7500m x DY: 15000m x = 7.5e6 x 1.5e7

Text S2. Parameters used in Autodyn (Ansys, Inc.)

Next, we used Autodyn to explore further transient crater dimensions, shock pressures, thermal radiation, and ejecta dispersal patterns based on defined input parameters.

Comet

Diam = 1270 m
Radius = 635 m = 635000 = 6.35e5 mm
Volume = 1.069e9 m³ = 1.069e18 mm³

X-center = 4100 = 4100000
Y-center = 13200 = 13200000
Y-semi-axis = 6.35e5
X-semi-axis = 6.35e5
X-velocity = 19798 mm/ms
Y-velocity = -19798 mm/ms

CometEnergy

Diam = 600 m
Radius = 300 m = 300000 = 3.0e5 mm
Energy 24500 Mt = 103000000000000000000 = 1.03e20

X-center = 4100 = 4100000
Y-center = 13200 = 13200000
Y-semi-axis = 3.2e5
X-semi-axis = 3.2e5
X-velocity = 19798 mm/ms
Y-velocity = -19798 mm/ms

References

1. Marcus R, Melosh HJ, Collins GS. Earth Impact Effects Program 2004 [updated 2023]. 2004:[Available from: <https://impact.ese.ic.ac.uk/ImpactEarth/ImpactEffects/>].
2. Collins GS, Melosh HJ, Marcus R. Earth impact effects program: a web-based computer program for calculating the regional environmental consequences of a meteoroid impact on Earth. Meteorit Planet Sci. 2005;40(2):817–40.